

INTEGRATED USE OF CONTEMPORARY COSTING METHODS: THE CASE OF THERMAL FACILITY

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ABSTRACT:

In this study, the integrated use of target costing and Kaizen costing methods for a sample thermal plant operation was carried out. The study was carried out on a thermal facility with 570 rooms. Case analysis technique was used as the research design in the study. The 2023 annual report, balance sheet and income statement of the sample enterprise were used as data collection tools. In addition, data collection was carried out from customers an importance-rating questionnaire in determining the importance levels of the service functions of the enterprise. 405 guests participated in this survey. Due to the increase in the Dollar/TL exchange rate by 38.15% in the relevant period, the calculation was made based on the Dollar/TL exchange rate while performing the Kaizen costing application.

First of all, in the study, the target cost index was determined with the target costing techniques of the sample enterprise. Then, Kaizen costing was implemented. Finally, the integrated use of target costing and Kaizen costing was realized. The findings show that the target cost index of the personnel sub-components of the front office-rooms, housekeeping, entertainment and general activities services of the sample enterprise remained below the desired level. A similar situation occurred in the preparation sub-component of food and beverage services. In line with the Kaizen cost target, it was concluded that the costs of the personnel sub-component in front office-rooms, housekeeping, entertainment and general activities services and the preparation sub-component in food and beverage services should be reduced.

Keywords: Target Costing, Kaizen Costing, Integrated Application, Thermal Tourism, Accommodation Sector.

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Research Paper

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the competitive environment for businesses has become more severe than ever. To have a sustainable competitive advantage, businesses must manufacture their products to meet the exact needs, wants, and demands of customers. As a result, businesses need to have higher-quality products in order to remain competitive and surpass the performance of other businesses in the market.

Quality means that goods and services are offered in accordance with the use and that the demands of customers are met. Quality product means compliance with quality standards in finished products. A business must strive to produce high-quality products to gain a competitive advantage over its competitors. When producing a high-quality product, the business must also take into account the quality costs incurred. In short, businesses need to produce high-quality products at low quality costs. In conclusion, quality and quality costs are vital for a business to survive in a highly competitive market.

Regardless of the field and purpose of a business, it effectively uses cost information to determine its profit target. Effective use of costs as a competitive advantage in hotels is only possible by determining and controlling costs. However, for the success and continuity of the event, it is important to redesign the cost information according to the developing technology and changing management approaches. For this reason, obtaining and evaluating cost information in the current system is an important problem area.

The product offered for sale in hotel businesses generally consists of a mix of goods and services. This product or service can be combined to meet requirements such as accommodation, food and beverage, and can be offered as a single product, combination of products, or independently. Since the source and formation of the cost elements of the components that make up the product or service mix differ, it is more difficult to charge the costs to the relevant products in this complex structure than other types of businesses.

Although the reasons affecting customer behavior are very diverse, price, company image and service quality are the leading factors for hotel businesses. In addition, considering that customers use digital channels well, the opportunity to see and compare

many businesses and information about them together reduces company loyalty. In addition, the intensity of competition, different production methods and processes, and the difficulties in the emergence and follow-up of costs in accommodation businesses where service and image factors are at the forefront make cost management more difficult than other types of businesses. For this reason, the use of modern costing techniques is important, especially in the accommodation sector.

In this study, an exemplary business operating in the accommodation sector was examined using contemporary costing techniques. The study was carried out on the thermal facility with 570 rooms, which was designed according to the mixed-use system of timeshare and hotel service in Balıkesir province.

In the first part of the study, the concept of cost management is explained. Here, the concepts of cost and classification are mentioned, cost management techniques and system are explained.

In the second part of the study, theoretical information about target costing and Kaizen is given. In the chapter, the objectives, features, advantages of target costing, the factors that play a role in determining target costing and the target costing management process are explained. Then, the features and advantages of Kaizen costing and its main components are explained. Finally, the Kaizen costing application process is given in the chapter.

The third part of the study is the method and application section. In this section, firstly, the integrated application technique is explained and general information about the sample business is given. In the application part of the study, first of all, the target costs were separated and the service functions were determined. Then, the relative importance of the service functions and the sub-components that make up the service were determined. The costs of each component were calculated and finally the target cost indices of the components were created. In the study, Kaizen cost targeting was carried out as the second method. Finally, the integrated use of target costing and Kaizen costing was realized.

2. LITERATURE SUMMARY

Increasing competition and the customer profile that has sought its rights through various platforms in recent years have made it imperative for every business to continuously improve its processes to stay ahead of the competition. This is achieved mainly through design and process designs and cost reduction. The actual design process depends on the product, and it is more important to determine the aspects of the products that require design than the design process (Azeez et al., 2020).

Tourism businesses are currently facing financial pressures that have led stakeholders to focus on the quality of information provided by cost systems in these businesses, and the greatest pressure faced by tourism businesses has been the inability of financial systems to handle planning, control, and decision-making processes (Stella et al., 2007). The activities have not provided appropriate explanations for the correct evaluation of cost elements in tourism enterprises and are not used much in the tourism and hospitality sector. For this reason, businesses and tourism businesses in general have started to practice transparency. In order to determine the costs of goods and services offered by tourism enterprises to their customers, it has also started to conduct a comprehensive review of the cost systems applied in the tourism sector, so that the review process aims to improve the quality of cost systems (Karagiorgos et al., 2008). Cost accounting systems determine the actual costs of production while determining costs, market expectations and customers in the field of both service and goods production. They can apply the advantages they have gained by applying methods such as using economic indicators to their sectors (Drury, 2013).

Reducing costs plays an important role in terms of maintaining activities and existence in the labor market, especially in businesses that are adversely affected by pandemic conditions - in all businesses in general, and in tourism businesses in particular. The use of modern management accounting methods contributes to the reduction of production costs of goods and services, strengthens the financial structures of enterprises and helps to compensate for losses caused by poor planning or lack of foresight (Horngren et al., 2002). For this reason, in this study, target costing and Kaizen costing approaches will be applied in thermal enterprises operating in the tourism sector.

Target costing is a strategic planning tool that takes a holistic view of products and their subassemblies and identifies opportunities for cost reduction and product improvement. Target costing also employs various techniques to set and achieve goals based on a business's strategic plans (Cooper & Slagmulder, 2017). The target cost method is considered as one of the modern administrative methods based on the presence of an integrated team consisting of various specialties that contribute to the determination of the items of service or commodity costs from the beginning of the service design phases and ends with the follow-up of the presentation to the customer and the update process according to the expectations of the customers and the market (Ansari et al., 2006; Cooper & Slagmulder, 2017; Helms et al., 2005; Zengin & Ada, 2010). Such a team of diverse expertise contributes to finding the true cost of services and facilitates the determination of prices for these services with reliability and stability (Ax et al., 2008).

Kaizen is a Japanese philosophy that is "a process of continuous improvement in quality, technology, business culture, productivity, safety, and leadership" (Barnes, 1996). It originated in Japan and literally means change (kai) for good (zen). Kaizen is more than just a methodology for continuous improvement. It is not a specific tool or set of tools to improve quality. In this respect, Kaizen is expressed as a journey and not a destination (Singh and Singh, 2009). The goal of Kaizen is to increase efficiency, reduce waste, eliminate unnecessary heavy work, and humanize the workplace. The Kaizen philosophy allows everyone to take responsibility for their processes and improve them. With Kaizen, employees at all levels of the organization are constantly monitoring and identifying opportunities for change and improvement (Doolen et al., 2003). Kaizen is not a one-time event but a process that happens every day. The cycle of Kaizen, which is expressed as its basic philosophy, has been abbreviated as PDCA (Plan, Do, Check, Act) (Darmawan et al., 2018). Kaizen started as part of the "Toyota Production System" as a method of involving the entire workforce to improve product quality. Kaizen has since become one of the main factors for the success of businesses. Kaizen in Japanese businesses is a way of life that includes everyone from the individual to the organization. In Japan, Kaizen is highly respected and considered an important tool on its way to becoming one of

the most powerful industrialized countries in the world. Kaizen has contributed greatly to Japan's competitive success (Prayuda, 2020). Kaizen is a human-oriented process that is used as a tool for change and problem solving. It has been defined as any continuous improvement process in any area of life (personal, social, home or work), and when applied to the workplace, Kaizen means continuous improvement that covers everyone from managers to workers (Imai, 1986).

Increasing competition forces business organizations to devise ways to enhance their competitiveness in the ever-changing global market. One of the ways businesses can improve their competitiveness is by improving the effectiveness of their systems. As defined above, Kaizen, which originated in Japan in the 1950s, is one of the tools widely used, especially in Asia, to improve elements related to the effectiveness of business organizations, the benefits of which are already well documented (Mureithi, 2013). The benefits of Kaizen management practices include immediate results, reduction of waste, improvement in all areas, reduction of overall production costs, sustainable improvement of quality, delivery dates, working conditions, ensuring motivation, discipline and standardization, and the participation of employees in the continuous improvement of the performance of the enterprise. When we look at the studies in the literature, this situation has been scientifically proven. In his research, Tiwari (2017) stated that it has helped many companies in India achieve better operational excellence and increase Kaizen efficiency. The Kaizen application focuses on enhancing productivity, quality, reducing costs, ensuring fast delivery, safety, and boosting employee morale to achieve better customer satisfaction and maximize the success of businesses (Arrasyid & Amaliyah, 2019). However, it has also been stated that in some cases, especially due to the origins of their organizations, the applicability of Kaizen to other countries with different cultures and different management styles still remains a failure (Recht & Wilderom, 1998). Considering this, different researchers have reported that the benefit of the Kaizen practice is along with both the social and technical dimensions of the organization. According to Abera (2015), a proper understanding of the policy tools, methods, culture, principles, and implementation techniques of the Kaizen philosophy will be an important step to address

and solve the current problems and challenges. Promoted as one of the tools of change and applicable to any field in need of improvement, Kaizen is a philosophy that is widely discussed and applied in various industries. Different researchers report that the implementation of Kaizen provides benefits in both the social and technical dimensions of the organization and includes cost reduction, increase of productivity, reduction of defects and improvement of employees' attitude (Bessant, 2003). The relationship between management and employees is very important, and Kaizen techniques contribute greatly to strengthening this relationship, as the efficiency and profitability of the business are the result of the mixed efforts of both parties. Kaizen brings together management and employees in a business for the better development of communication and is a means of inspiration of the best alternative and a sense of membership and belonging. This type of connection builds trust on both parties for the ultimate goal of the business (Imai, 1997). However, research shows that some of the reasons why businesses fail to apply the Kaizen philosophy correctly for many reasons are misunderstanding the Kaizen philosophy and how to apply it correctly. The finding, according to a study conducted by Desta et al. (2014) in the manufacturing industries of Northern Ethiopia, shows that Kaizen helps to reduce waste affecting the business and gets the results that firms need to get before initiating the Kaizen strategy for improvement. However, it has demonstrated the importance of the Kaizen philosophy in order to review business performances and identify strengths and weaknesses and to understand how it should be applied to achieve a satisfactory result. In addition, as the Abera (2015) research shows, different scholars in the region argue that a proper understanding of the policy tools, methods, culture, principles, and implementation techniques of Kaizen philosophy will be an important step towards addressing and solving current problems. Additionally, it is suggested that in countries with diverse socio-cultural contexts, Kaizen should be conducted under appropriate leadership and with regulations that reflect the uniqueness of the intended society (Ohno et al., 2009). In another study, Sani & Allahverdzadeh (2012) associate a target cost planning process with the Kaizen process after the products are put into production. They noted that other businesses,

such as those with short to medium product life cycles, are more focused on target costing. Their approach to continuous improvement is to have several product generations at different stages of design and development (i.e., different stages of target costing). Other businesses place more emphasis on Kaizen during their operations, in more mature markets with longer product lifecycles. Kaizen essentially seeks to ensure that everyone in the business is constantly reconsidering how the task is undertaken and whether there is a better way to do it (Williamson, 1997).

This study differs from other studies in terms of its practice in a thermal facility that combines both hotel and timeshare services, as well as the practice of the improvement areas that emerged as a result of the calculations in the next year and the results of the study.

3. INTEGRATED USE OF CONTEMPORARY COSTING METHODS: THE CASE OF THERMAL FACILITY

3.1. Purpose of the Research

With the increasing competitive environment in recent years, cost has become an important factor, especially in thermal enterprises. Thermal enterprises, where pricing policies are lower compared to businesses in marine tourism, have problems in costing with the recent Covid-19 pandemic and the subsequent foreign exchange crisis (Tengilimoğlu, 2021; Köse & Ayhün, 2020; Kabacık, 2021), and as a result, costing studies in thermal enterprises gain importance. For this reason, the aim of the research is to determine and implement target costing and Kaizen costing approaches in the sample thermal enterprise operating in the tourism sector where there is intense competition and to analyze their effects on service production processes. In addition, it is aimed to determine whether costs can be reduced by using target costing and Kaizen costing approaches together (integrated practice) in the service production process in the sample enterprise.

For this purpose, the research questions of the study are as follows;

- Are target costing and Kaizen costing practices carried out in the sample business?
- To what extent will the costs be affected by target costing and Kaizen costing approaches in the sample business?

- What are the effects of applying target costing and Kaizen costing approaches together on the sample business?

- What are the negativities encountered in the process of target costing and Kaizen costing practices in the sample business?

3.2. Method of the Research

The aim of the research is to determine and implement target costing and Kaizen costing approaches in sample thermal enterprise and to analyze their effects on service production processes. For this purpose, the research will be carried out on a thermal enterprise that has been operating for 13 years in the Edremit district of Balıkesir. According to the Thermal Tourism Master Plan (2007-2023) of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism of the Republic of Turkey, there are 59 thermal tourism centers across the country. 47 of them are in the Southern Marmara, Southern Aegean, Phrygia and Central Anatolia regions. The sample enterprise to be applied in the research is in Balıkesir province and in the Southern Marmara Region. According to the plan, there are 29 geothermal fields and 11 thermal tourism centers in the Southern Marmara Region. There are 16 geothermal fields and 5 thermal tourism centers in Balıkesir province. Therefore, the universe of the research is this region. The sample enterprise currently has 250 personnel. The sample business has 570 rooms and is both a thermal hotel and a timeshare facility. Case analysis technique will be used in the study to be carried out on the sample business. Case analysis is a qualitative research design that examines a single or several facts, events or phenomena in depth. Case analysis is the in-depth examination of a current social phenomenon in its own context with data collected through various data collection techniques. In other words, case analysis is the empirical investigation of a current phenomenon in a real-life context, especially in cases where the context and boundaries of the facts are not clearly defined. Creswell (2020) defines case analysis as a qualitative research design in which the researcher examines one or more situations limited over time in depth with various data collection tools (observation, interview, document review) and reveals situations and situation-related themes. In case analysis, it is tried to understand how the situation works by collecting information about a person, environment or event related to a special situation. According to Merriam (2013), case

analysis is research conducted to investigate an example, phenomenon or social event in a holistic way. Again, Creswell (2020) defined case analysis as a research design in which the researcher examines one or more situations (case-case study) in depth with the help of observations, interviews and documents, and the situations and themes related to the situation in question are defined and interpreted.

During the implementation of the research, the relevant documents of the sample business were examined, and the calculation of the target cost was made based on the salable room price and quantity. Then, the costing procedure carried out in the sample enterprise was examined and target costing was applied. However, improvements in the service process were looked at as another target cost reduction. Improvement amounts in the service process were calculated with the Kaizen cost target. It was evaluated in which areas and in what amount the improvements to be made with the Kaizen costing approach should be made. In target costing and Kaizen practice, the Dollar/TL exchange rate was used in cost calculations. As a result of the 38.15% increase in the US Dollar against TL within 1 year during the time period in which the relevant study was carried out, the target cost per room value determined as TL remains quite low. For this reason, the Dollar/TL exchange rate was used in order to carry out a healthier analysis process.

3.3. Scope of the Research

The research covers target costing and Kaizen costing approaches, which can be used by every business, including the business analyzed in this study, to develop strategies, plans and designs that strategically position them in today's highly competitive, diverse and complex business environment, which enable the costing of

businesses to be revealed and which are effective in reducing production and service costs. This research is about providing information to many businesses and business managements, especially those operating in the thermal tourism sector, about change, continuous improvement (Kaizen practice) and how employee performance is increased. However, in line with the scope of the research, it has been preferred because it will help policy makers as a tool or input for their decision-making, and will help to gain in-depth knowledge about target costing and Kaizen philosophy.

3.4. Evaluation of Findings

Under this heading, the values of the cost data of the sample enterprise examined within the scope of the research were examined within the framework of target costing and Kaizen costing methods and the findings were evaluated under sub-headings.

3.4.1. Summary Financial Information of the Sample Business

Summary financial information of the sample enterprise examined within the scope of the research is given in the table below.

Looking at the summary financial statement (Table 1) of the sample enterprise, it is seen that total revenues were targeted at TL 167.8 million while amounted to TL 175.6 million. The deviation in total revenues is 4.67%. The largest share in total revenues belongs to the front office-accommodation department. The 2023 revenue target for the front office-accommodation department was set at TL 116.5 million, but it was realized as TL 109 million with a deviation of -6.4%. In the food and beverage (F&B) department, the revenue generated is 39.72% higher than the targeted revenue.

Table 1. Summary Financial Information-2023

	Targeted	Realized	Deviation (%)
Department Revenues			
Front Desk-Accommodation	116,515,140	109,065,958	-6.40
F&B	38,115,807	53,256,859	39.72
Other	13,175,232	13,318,922	1.1
Total Revenues	167,806,179	175,641,739	4.67
Department Expenses			
Front Desk-Accommodation	20,426,356	23,213,848	13.65
F&B	35,979,711	45,036,971	25.18
Other	8,343,579	9,898,084	18.63
Total Expenses	64,749,645	78,148,903	20.70
Department Profitability			
Front Desk-Accommodation	96,088,785	85,852,109	-10.65
F&B	2,136,097	8,219,887	284.81
Other	4,831,653	3,420,839	-29.2
Total Profitability	103,056,535	97,492,835	-5.4
Non-Revenue Departments (GGD)			
General Management	24,979,186	28,039,348	12.25
GGD (Other) Expenses	49,497,606	33,571,920	-32.17
Business Wide			
Operating Total Expenses	139,226,437	139,760,171	0.38
Business Total Profitability	28,579,743	35,881,568	25.55

Looking at Table 1 for the total expenses of the enterprise, it is seen that a total expense of 64.7 million TL is targeted. The realized value in 2023 increased by 20.7% to TL 78.1 million. The largest deviation in the business's expenses was in the food and beverage (F&B) department at 25.18%. The expense in this department is the highest expense item among the departments and it is seen that this amount is 45 million TL.

Such a deviation for total expenses also affected the total profitability of the departments. While the amount targeted by the company for the total profitability of the departments is 103 million TL, it is seen that the realized profitability is 97.4 million TL. Here, too, there is a deviation of -5.4% from the target. It can be stated that this situation is due to increases in expense items outside the target. If revenues for front office-accommodation services were below the target and expenses were higher than targeted, the targeted profitability was negatively affected. Here, the food and beverage (F&B) department achieved profitability well above the target, with a deviation of 284.81%.

When the expenses of the non-revenue-generating departments within the enterprise are

examined, it is seen that the general administrative expenses were targeted as 24.9 million TL, but they were realized as 28 million TL with a deviation of 12.25%. In the expenses of technical units, an expense of 33.57 million TL was realized against an expense target of 49.5 million TL. For this reason, there was a deviation of -32.2% in the expenses of the technical unit.

Looking at the total expenses of the enterprise, it is seen that there is a target of 139.2 million TL. The actual value was very close to the target and amounted to TL 139.7 million with a deviation of 0.38%. However, the total profitability of the enterprise was above the target. The total operating profit targeted for 2023 is 28.6 million TL, while the actual profit is 35.8 million TL. Accordingly, the total profitability of the enterprise was 25.5% higher than the target.

3.4.2. Findings on Target Costing

3.4.2.1. Calculation of Actual Sales Price and Costs Per Room of the Sample Business

During the calculation of the actual sales price and cost per room of the sample enterprise, the 2023 annual report of the enterprise was used. It was

observed that the sales revenues of the business for 2023 were 175,641,739 TL and the number of rooms sold in 2023 was 123,198. In the face of this situation, the determination of the actual sales price per room of the business will be calculated with the following formula.

$$\text{Actual Sales Price Per Room} = \frac{\text{Total Revenues for the Year 2023}}{\text{Number of Rooms Sold in 2023}}$$

The above formula is the formula that will be used to calculate the actual sales price per room of the business. Together with the data obtained from the income statement and annual report, the actual sales price per room of the business is as follows.

$$\text{Actual Sales Price Per Room} = \frac{175,641,739}{123,198}$$

Accordingly, the actual sales price per room of the business was calculated as 1,425.69 TL.

Another value to be calculated for the sample business is the actual cost per room. For this, the calculation was carried out using the following formula with the data obtained from the income statement and annual report of the enterprise for 2023.

$$\text{Actual Cost Per Room} = \frac{\text{Total Expenses for the Year 2023}}{\text{Number of Rooms Sold in 2023}}$$

The formula above is the formula that will give the actual sales cost per room. The total expenses of the sample enterprise examined within the scope of the research for 2023 amounted to TL 139,760,171. Accordingly, the actual cost per room of the business is calculated as follows.

$$\text{Actual Cost Per Room} = \frac{139,760,171}{123,198}$$

The value obtained from the above formula is 1,134.44 TL. In other words, the actual cost value per room of the sample business is 1,134.44 TL.

It is seen that the actual sales price per room for the sample business for 2023 is 1,425.69 TL and the actual cost value per room is 1,134.44 TL. Based on this, the profit per room of the business in 2023, or in other words, the profit obtained from a room, is calculated with the following formula.

$$\text{Actual Profit Per Room} = \text{Actual Price Per Room} - \text{Actual Cost Per Room}$$

According to this formula;

$$\text{Actual Profit Per Room} = 1,425.69 - 1,134.44$$

$$\text{Actual profit per room} = 291.25 \text{ TL.}$$

Accordingly, it is seen that the actual profit margin of the enterprise for 2023 is 20%.

3.4.2.2. Calculation of the Target Cost of the Sample Enterprise

In order to calculate the target costs of the sample enterprise, the calculation was carried out with the data obtained from the annual report of the enterprise for 2023. In calculating the target costing, the target profit must be subtracted from the target sales price determined by the enterprise in accordance with the market conditions.

Accordingly, the target sales of the sample business for 2024 are 300,000,000 TL. When the target profit margin is determined as 25%, the target profit is 75,000,000 TL. According to this information, the target cost of the sample business;

$$\text{Target Cost} = \text{Target Sales} - \text{Target Profit}$$

$$\text{Target Cost} = 300,000,000 - 75,000,000$$

$$\text{Target Cost} = 225,000,000 \text{ TL.}$$

The target room sales set by the sample business for 2024 is 150,000. Accordingly, the target cost per room of the sample business for 2024 is;

$$\text{Target Cost Per Room}_{2024} = \frac{225,000,000}{150,000}$$

$$\text{Target Cost Per Room}_{2024} = 1,500 \text{ TL.}$$

3.4.2.3. Decomposition of Target Cost

In the target cost method, determining the target cost alone is not sufficient. This also needs to be separated by departments throughout the entire business. For this reason, in the sample enterprise where service production is carried out, it is necessary to first determine the service functions and then to determine the relative importance for the service functions. After these processes, it is necessary to determine the components that will make up each service and determine their costs. Finally, target cost indices of the determined components should be created and optimized. All these processes were carried out under separate headings.

3.4.2.3.1. Determination of Service Functions of the Sample Enterprise

Within the scope of decomposing the target cost, service functions should be determined first. Within the services offered in the sample business, the service functions are briefly explained in the following paragraphs.

Front Desk-Rooms Services: The front desk is the first department of the hotel that contacts the guest. This department performs various functions such as reservation, reception, registration, room allocation, and payment of bills

for a resident guest. The guest keeps in touch with the front desk for information and any assistance. Therefore, it can be said that the Front Office is the center of hotel operations. Along with the front desk-rooms services, welcoming the guests, placing the belongings in the rooms, having technical support related to the rooms, and check-in and check-out procedures are carried out. Within the scope of the front office-rooms services of the sample business, there are welcome/information, technical support, bellboy service and check-in/check-out procedures.

Housekeeping: The goal of all hotels or businesses offering accommodation services is to provide their customers with a clean, attractive, comfortable and welcoming environment that offers value for money. Nothing conveys a stronger message in the hospitality industry than cleanliness. No level of service, smiling face, or grandeur can equal the feeling a guest feels when they enter a clean, tidy, and properly arranged room. Both management and guests feel that keeping the space clean and tidy is a necessity for a hotel to have a fair price and get repeat business. Housekeeping services include room cleaning, garbage disposal, cleaning of various surfaces, cleaning of common areas and cleaning of toilets. The housekeeping services of the sample business include room cleaning service, general area cleaning service and complete provision of amenities such as shampoo, conditioner, etc.

Food and Beverage: "Food and beverage" is a general term used in hospitality and typically

represents the food and beverage items required at events, banquets, or dining services. The food and beverage department in a hotel consists of various units and a large number of staff members to meet the needs of customers inside or outside the hotel. In the sample business, there are sub-functions of service speed, taste, satiety/portion, hygiene and presentation/visuality of food and beverages within the scope of food and beverage services.

Entertainment: Hospitality entertainment systems encompass events, theater performances, musical shows, and other entertainment activities that provide an element of entertainment for guests. The availability of entertainment options for both children and adults is one of the factors that influence a guest's choice of hotel. The sub-functions within the scope of entertainment service within the sample business are animation, mini club, night club, gymnastics and sports activities.

General Activities: Within the scope of this service, there are activities offered indoors or outdoors within the hotel. Within the scope of the general activities function of the sample business, there are outdoor pools, indoor pools, children's pool, Turkish bath and sauna, and fitness and SPA sub-functions.

Finally, the service functions of the sample business are shown in a summary form in the figure below.

Figure 1. Sample Business Service Functions

3.4.2.3.2. Determination of the Relative Importance of Service Functions

The determination of the relative importance of service functions is calculated in line with the preferences of the customers. In line with the questionnaire given to sample business customers and consisting of the service functions and sub-functions of the business, the relative importance of the service functions is determined. This questionnaire was created by us and consists of 22 questions. Accordingly, customers were asked to give importance ratings to each sub-function and rank them from one to five. A survey was created with Google Forms and a link to the survey was sent to the phones of approximately 1000 guests who received accommodation services in July 2024. 405 guests (approximately 40%) participated in this survey. The questionnaire is attached to the study.

The sum of the values given for each sub-function constitutes the score. By proportioning the sub-function score to the total service score, the relative importance levels are obtained as a percentage (%). According to the findings, the relative importance of each service function and sub-function was determined. The findings are shown in tables below.

Table 2. Front Office-Rooms Services Sub-Functions Relative Importance Levels

Sub-Functions	Relative Importance Ratings	
	Rating	%
Welcome/Information	1758	0.31
Technical Support (Cable TV, Wi-Fi, Internet, Safe)	1304	0.23
Bellboy Service	1134	0.20
Check-in/Check-out Procedures	1474	0.26
Total	5670	1.00

In Table 2, the relative importance levels of the sub-functions of the front office-rooms services are given in line with the information obtained from the customers. Accordingly, welcome/information is of the highest importance with 0.31. Check-in/check-out 0.26; Technical support (cable TV, Wi-Fi, internet, safe) 0.23 and bellboy service 0.20 is important.

Table 3. Housekeeping Sub-Functions Relative Importance Levels

Sub-Functions	Relative Importance Ratings	
	Rating	%
Room Cleaning	1799	0.37
General Area Cleaning	1652	0.34
Amenities	1409	0.29
Total	4860	1.00

Table 3 shows the relative importance of the sub-functions of the housekeeping services of the sample enterprise by its customers. According to the findings, the sub-function with the highest importance was room cleaning with 0.37, followed by general area cleaning with 0.34 and amenities with 0.29.

Table 4. Food and Beverage Services Sub-Functions Relative Importance Levels

Sub-Functions	Relative Importance Ratings	
	Rating	%
Service Speed	1160	0.19
Flavor	1281	0.21
Filling/Portion	1134	0.19
Hygiene	1463	0.24
Presentation/Visuality	1037	0.17
Total	6075	1.00

In Table 4, when the relative importance levels of the sub-functions of food and beverage services are examined, it is seen that hygiene ranks first with 0.24. Then there is flavor with 0.21 and serving speed and heartiness/portion with 0.19. In the last place is the presentation/visuality sub-function with 0.17.

Table 5. Relative Importance of Entertainment Service Sub-Functions

Sub-Functions	Relative Importance Ratings	
	Rating	%
Animation	1219	0.20
Mini Club	1338	0.22
Night Club	1207	0.20
Gymnastics	1034	0.17
Sports Activities	1277	0.21
Total	6075	1.00

Table 5 shows the relative importance of the entertainment service sub-functions. Accordingly, mini club had the highest importance level with 0.22, followed by sports activities with 0.21. The

importance of the animation and night club sub-functions is 0.20 and finally the importance of the gymnastics sub-function is 0.17.

Table 6. General Activities Service Sub-Functions Relative Importance Levels

Sub-Functions	Relative Importance Ratings	
	Rating	%
Outdoor Pools	1286	0.21
Indoor Pools	1265	0.21
Children's Pool	1160	0.19
Turkish Bath and Sauna	1213	0.20
Fitness & SPA	1151	0.19
Total	6075	1.00

The last service of the sample business is general activities. Data on this are shown in Table 6. According to the findings, among the sub-functions of the general activities service, the sub-function with the highest degree of importance according to the customers was indoor and outdoor pools with 0.21. After these sub-functions, the highest importance level was 0.20 and the Turkish bath and sauna sub-function. The relative importance levels of the children's pool and fitness and SPA sub-functions are 0.19.

3.4.2.3.3. Determination of the Components to Make Up the Service

The components that will make up the service in the accommodation sector are the components that enable the production of the service. In this respect, the service functions in the sample business are determined as front office-rooms services, housekeeping, food and beverage services, entertainment services and general activities. However, there are also sub-components that make up the service functions. The sub-components that make up the service functions specific to the sample business are as follows.

Front Office-Rooms;

- Staff
- Printed documents-stationery
- Consumables

Housekeeping;

- Staff
- Cleaning Supplies
- Amenities
- Consumables

Food and Beverage Service;

- Staff
- Preparation
- Presentation
- Cooking

Entertainment;

- Staff
- Consumables

General Activities;

- Staff
- Cleaning Supplies
- Consumables

3.4.2.3.4. Determination of the Cost of Each Component

After determining the sub-components of the service functions of the sample enterprise, the cost of each component should be determined. For this purpose, the annual report of the sample enterprise and the information obtained from the accounting unit were collected and the cost calculation of the sub-components of the service functions was carried out. Component costs for front desk-room services, housekeeping, food and beverage services, entertainment services, and general activities are detailed in the tables below.

Table 7. Front Office-Rooms Services Sub-Components

Components	Component Cost (TL)	Cost Percentage (%)
Staff	5,908,209.30	97.08
Printed Documents-Stationery	154,172.00	2.53
Consumables	23,827.80	0.39
Total	6,086,209.10	100

Table 7 shows the cost and cost percentages of the sub-components of the front office-rooms service. Accordingly, the sub-component with the highest cost share in front office-rooms services is personnel cost with 5,908,209.30 TL. This value has a share of 97.08% in the total cost. The cost of printed documents and stationery is seen as 154,172 TL (2.53%). The sub-component with the lowest cost percentage among the front office-rooms services is consumables with 0.39%. For 2023, the cost of consumables in front office-rooms services is shown as 23,827.80 TL.

Table 8. Housekeeping Sub-Components

Components	Component Cost (TL)	Cost Percentage (%)
Staff	13,785,821.70	87.82
Cleaning Supplies	1,252,746.00	7.98
Amenities	604,446.00	3.85
Consumables	55,598.20	0.35
Total	15,698,611.90	100

The costs of the housekeeping sub-components are given in Table 8. As in front desk-rooms services, the sub-component with the highest cost percentage was personnel (87.82%). In 2023, there is a personnel cost of 13,785,821.70 TL. The cost of cleaning materials was TRY 1,252,746 (7.98%), while the cost of amenities was TRY 604,446 (3.85%). Finally, the cost of consumables was 55,598.20 TL (0.35%).

Table 9. Food and Beverage Services Sub-Components

Components	Component Cost (TL)	Cost Percentage (%)
Staff	7,926,520.00	28.11
Preparation	19,715,070.00	69.93
Presentation	521,083.00	1.85
Cooking	314,680.00	0.11
Total	28,194,141.00	100

In Table 9, component costs and cost percentages of food and beverage services sub-components are given. The highest component cost belongs to the preparation sub-component with 19,715,070 TL. The percentage of cost in the service is 69.93%. The personnel cost is 7,926,520 TL. The share of personnel in the total cost is 28.11%. The cost of the presentation sub-component of food and beverage services was 521,083 TL (1.85%), while the cooking cost was 31,468 TL (0.11%).

Table 10. Entertainment Services Sub-Components

Components	Component Cost (TL)	Cost Percentage (%)
Staff	1,180,000.00	95.01
Consumables	61,963.00	4.99
Total	1,241,963.00	100

Entertainment services include animation, mini club, night club, gymnastics and sports activities. The sub-components used in the provision of these services are divided into personnel and consumables. The sample business does not keep separate cost records for each service, but keeps records of personnel and consumable costs for all

services. According to the data in Table 10, personnel cost has a large share of 95.01% (1,180,000 TL) in terms of cost percentage in the provision of services. The cost of consumables is stated as 61,963 TL (4.99%).

Table 11. General Activities Sub-Components

Components	Component Cost (TL)	Cost Percentage (%)
Staff	6,343,203.00	83.55
Cleaning Supplies	1,001,820.00	13.20
Consumables	246,684.00	3.25
Total	7,591,707.00	100

Finally, the sub-component costs of the general activities in the sample enterprise are given in Table 11. Accordingly, the highest cost is personnel cost with 6,343,203 TL (83.55%). Here, the highest cost for the service provided as pools, fitness and SPA belongs to the staff. Of the sub-components, cleaning is in the form of pool chemicals, fitness and SPA cleaning materials and other chemicals, and the component cost is 1,001,820 TL. The cost percentage was calculated as 13.2%. Finally, the component cost of consumables used in general activities was 246,684 TL (3.25%).

3.4.2.3.5. Determining the Relative Importance of the Components That Make Up the Service

The calculation of the relative importance of the components that make up the service is carried out with the relative importance of the sub-functions of the services and the percentages of the service coverage of the sub-components of the services obtained from the enterprise. The coverage percentages of the sub-components were created as a result of the interviews with the relevant department managers and the business manager. Here, while calculating the relative importance percentages of the components, comparison was made with the help of matrix and calculation was performed. The importance levels of the service sub-functions and the service coverage values of the service sub-components are multiplied separately and the combined total is obtained. The finding obtained gives the relative importance percentages of the components. The values of front office-room services, housekeeping, food and beverage services, entertainment services and general activities of the sample business are given in detail in the tables below, and how the calculations are carried out is shown under the tables.

Table 12. Front Office-Rooms Services Sub-Functions Relative Importance Levels

FRONT DESK ROOMS					
FRONT OFFICE ROOMS SUB-COMPONENTS	IMPORTANCE OF SUB-FUNCTIONS				Relative Importance of Components (%)
	Welcome	Technical Support	Bellboy	Check-in/out	
	0.31	0.23	0.20	0.26	
Staff	0.80	0.60	0.90	0.80	77
Printed Documents-Stationery	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.10	8
Consumables	0.10	0.30	0.10	0.10	15
TOTAL	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	100

In Table 12, firstly, the importance levels of the sub-functions obtained from the customers of the front office-rooms services (0.31; 0.23; 0.20 and 0.26, respectively) appear above the table. The ratio of sub-components to meet the service is given according to the information obtained from the business managers to what extent each sub-component meets the sub-function. Accordingly, the calculation of the relative importance of the personnel sub-component is as follows.

Relative importance of personnel sub-component = (Importance of the reception function * share of the personnel component) + (Importance of the technical support function * share of the personnel component) + (Importance of the bellboy function * share of the personnel component) + (Importance of the check-in/out function * share of the personnel component)

This formula is applied to all sub-components and calculated as follows:

$$\text{Relative importance of personnel subcomponent} = (0.31 \times 0.8) + (0.23 \times 0.6) + (0.2 \times 0.9) + (0.26 \times 0.8) = 0.77$$

$$\text{Relative importance of printed document stationery sub-component} = (0.31 \times 0.1) + (0.23 \times 0.1) + (0.2 \times 0) + (0.26 \times 0.1) = 0.08$$

$$\text{Consumables subcomponent relative importance} = (0.31 \times 0.1) + (0.23 \times 0.3) + (0.2 \times 0.1) + (0.26 \times 0.1) = 0.15$$

Accordingly, it can be said that the personnel (77%) sub-component has the highest importance among the relative importance of the front office-rooms services sub-components.

Table 13. Housekeeping Sub-Functions Relative Importance Levels

HOUSEKEEPING				
HOUSEKEEPING SUB-COMPONENTS	IMPORTANCE OF SUB-FUNCTIONS			Relative Importance of Components (%)
	Room Cleaning	General Area Cleaning	Amenities	
	0.37	0.34	0.29	
Staff	0.50	0.70	0.10	45
Cleaning Supplies	0.40	0.10	0.00	18
Amenities	0.00	0.00	0.90	26
Consumables	0.10	0.20	0.00	11
TOTAL	1.00	1.00	1.00	100

The importance levels of the housekeeping sub-functions and the coverage percentages of the sub-components are given in Table 13. The calculation of the relative importance of each sub-component is shown below.

$$\text{Relative importance of personnel subcomponent} = (0.37 \times 0.5) + (0.34 \times 0.7) + (0.29 \times 0.1) = 0.45$$

$$\text{Relative importance of cleaning materials subcomponent} = (0.37 \times 0.4) + (0.34 \times 0.1) + (0.29 \times 0) = 0.18$$

$$\text{Relative importance of the subcomponent of amenities} = (0.37 \times 0) + (0.34 \times 0) + (0.29 \times 0.9) = 0.26$$

$$\text{Consumables subcomponent relative importance} = (0.37 \times 0.1) + (0.34 \times 0.2) + (0.29 \times 0) = 0.11$$

The sub-component with the highest relative importance among housekeeping services was the personnel sub-component with 45%. This is

followed by amenities with 26%, cleaning materials with 18% and consumables with 11%.

Table 14. Food and Beverage Services Sub-Functions Relative Importance Levels

FOOD & DRINK						
FOOD AND BEVERAGE SUB-COMPONENTS	IMPORTANCE OF SUB-FUNCTIONS					Relative Importance of Components (%)
	Service Speed	Flavor	Heartiness Portion	Hygiene	Presentation Visuality	
	0.19	0.21	0.19	0.24	0.17	
Staff	0.30	0.40	0.30	0.60	0.50	43
Preparation	0.30	0.30	0.10	0.20	0.20	22
Presentation	0.10	0.10	0.50	0.10	0.20	19
Cooking	0.30	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.10	16
TOTAL	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	100

The importance levels of the sub-functions of the food and beverage service and the coverage percentages of the sub-components are given in Table 14. In line with the data obtained, the calculation of the relative importance of each component is as follows:

Relative importance of personnel subcomponent = $(0.19 \times 0.3) + (0.21 \times 0.4) + (0.19 \times 0.3) + (0.24 \times 0.6) + (0.17 \times 0.5) = 0.43$

Preparation subcomponent relative importance = $(0.19 \times 0.3) + (0.21 \times 0.3) + (0.19 \times 0.1) + (0.24 \times 0.2) + (0.17 \times 0.2) = 0.22$

Presentation subcomponent relative importance = $(0.19 \times 0.1) + (0.21 \times 0.1) + (0.19 \times 0.5) + (0.24 \times 0.1) + (0.17 \times 0.2) = 0.19$

Baking subcomponent relative importance = $(0.19 \times 0.3) + (0.21 \times 0.2) + (0.19 \times 0.1) + (0.24 \times 0.1) + (0.17 \times 0.1) = 0.16$

According to the findings, the sub-component with the highest relative importance in the sub-components of food and beverage service is personnel with 43%. The relative importance of the preparation sub-component is 22%, the relative importance of the presentation sub-component is 19%, and finally the relative importance of the cooking sub-component is 16%.

Table 15. Relative Importance of Entertainment Services Sub-Functions

ENTERTAINMENT						
ENTERTAINMENT SUB-COMPONENTS	IMPORTANCE OF SUB-FUNCTIONS					Relative Importance of Components (%)
	Animation	Mini Club	Night Club	Gymnastics	Sports Activities	
	0.20	0.22	0.20	0.17	0.21	
Staff	0.60	0.50	0.50	0.80	0.60	59
Consumables	0.40	0.50	0.50	0.20	0.40	41
TOTAL	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	100

Entertainment services sub-components are divided into personnel and consumables. In Table 15, the coverage percentages of the sub-components and the importance levels of the sub-functions are given. Accordingly, the relative importance levels of the sub-components are as follows:

Relative importance of personnel subcomponent = $(0.2 \times 0.6) + (0.22 \times 0.5) + (0.2 \times 0.5) + (0.17 \times 0.8) + (0.21 \times 0.6) = 0.59$

Consumables subcomponent relative importance = $(0.2 \times 0.4) + (0.22 \times 0.5) + (0.2 \times 0.5) + (0.17 \times 0.2) + (0.21 \times 0.4) = 0.41$

According to the findings, the relative importance of the personnel sub-component is higher.

Table 16. General Activities Sub-Functions Relative Importance Levels

GENERAL ACTIVITIES						
GENERAL ACTIVITIES SUB-COMPONENTS	IMPORTANCE OF SUB-FUNCTIONS					Relative Importance of Components (%)
	Outdoor Pools	Indoor Pools	Children's Pool	Turkish Bath and Sauna	Fitness & SPA	
	0.21	0.21	0.19	0.20	0.19	
Staff	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.40	32
Cleaning Supplies	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.40	48
Consumables	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	20
TOTAL	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	100

Finally, the importance levels of the sub-functions of the general activities and the coverage percentages of the sub-components are given in Table 16. Accordingly, the importance levels of the sub-components are as follows.

Relative importance of personnel subcomponent = $(0.21 \times 0.3) + (0.21 \times 0.3) + (0.19 \times 0.3) + (0.2 \times 0.3) + (0.19 \times 0.4) = 0.32$

Relative importance of the cleaning materials subcomponent = $(0.2 \times 0.5) + (0.22 \times 0.5) + (0.2 \times 0.5) + (0.17 \times 0.5) + (0.21 \times 0.4) = 0.48$

Consumables subcomponent relative importance = $(0.2 \times 0.2) + (0.22 \times 0.2) + (0.2 \times 0.2) + (0.17 \times 0.2) + (0.21 \times 0.2) = 0.20$

Accordingly, the sub-component with the highest relative importance among the sub-components in general activities is cleaning materials with 48%. Personnel have a relative importance rating of 32%, while consumables have a relative importance rating of 20%.

3.4.2.3.6. Creation and Optimization of Target Cost Index of Components

The creation of the target cost index is obtained by dividing the importance levels of the sub-components obtained in the previous sections by the cost share in the service. Together with the calculation of the target cost index, it enables the creation of the target cost index of each sub-component. In this respect, it also reveals in which

sub-components arrangements should be made to reach the target cost. The creation of the target cost index is realized with the following formula.

$$\text{Component Target Cost Index} = \frac{\text{Component Relative Importance}}{\text{Component Cost Share}}$$

It is desirable for the component target cost index **to be 1**. Because the index is 1, it indicates that the cost incurred for the component is equal to the degree of importance attributed to that component by customers. In other words, this situation indicates that the cost incurred by the enterprise for the creation of the component and the importance given by the customers to the service component in question are balanced.

An index **above 1 indicates** that a service component that customers attach more importance to is offered by the business at a relatively **lower cost**. In this case, the business needs to **focus on** development and value-enhancing activities for the relevant component.

In contrast, if the index **is below 1**, it reveals that the importance of the service component is lower than the component cost. In other words, it is understood that the business produces this component **at a higher cost** compared to the importance attributed by customers. In this case, it is concluded that the enterprise **should take cost-reducing measures** for the relevant component (Cooper & Slagmulder, 2017; Ansari et al., 2006; Zengin & Ada, 2010).

Table 17. Front Office-Rooms Services-Target Cost Indices of Components

Sub-Components	Relative Importance of Sub-Components	Percentage of Cost of Sub-Components	Cost Index of Sub-Components
Staff	0.770	0.970	0.790
Printed Documents-Stationery	0.080	0.0250	3.200
Consumables	0.150	0.004	37.500

Table 17 shows the cost index calculation for the sub-components of the front office-rooms services of the sample enterprise. The first column gives the relative importance of the sub-components, which is created by the importance levels obtained from the sample business customers. The second column gives the cost percentages of the sub-components for that service group in line with the data obtained from the sample enterprise. Accordingly, target cost indices were obtained above 1 in printed documents-stationery and consumables sub-components in front office-rooms services. The target cost index of the

personnel sub-component remained below 1. Accordingly, the sample business incurs lower costs for printed documents-stationery and consumables sub-components than the importance given by the customers. On the other hand, the situation is the opposite for the personnel sub-component. Here, the cost of the sample operation was obtained higher than the customer importance levels. It may be recommended to reduce the personnel costs of the business and to increase the functionality for printed documents-stationery and consumable sub-components.

Table 18. Housekeeping-Target Cost Indices of Components

Sub-Components	Relative Importance of Sub-Components	Percentage of Cost of Sub-Components	Cost Index of Sub-Components
Staff	0.45	0.8800	0.51
Cleaning Supplies	0.18	0.0790	2.27
Amenities	0.26	0.0380	6.84
Consumables	0.11	0.0035	3.,40

The relative importance levels and cost percentages of the housekeeping sub-components are given in Table 18. Target cost indices of the sub-components are created by dividing the relative importance of the sub-components by the cost percentages of the sub-components. Among the target cost indices obtained, there is only a personnel sub-component below 1. The target cost indices of the sub-components of cleaning materials, amenities and consumables were obtained above 1. Accordingly, the personnel costs of the sample enterprise in housekeeping were high compared to their importance. In this respect, it can be recommended that the sample business reduce personnel costs. On the other hand, the

importance levels determined by the customers for cleaning materials, amenities and consumables were higher than the cost percentages for the relevant sub-components of the sample enterprise. In other words, the exemplary business has realized the sub-components that are important for customers at low cost. However, the fact that the importance of customers to the relevant sub-components is higher than the costs may reveal that there are situations that the sample business needs to improve for the relevant components. For example, customers attach high importance to boucle materials, so the sample business may need to increase the variety of boucle materials.

Table 19. Food and Beverage Services-Target Cost Indices of Components

Sub-Components	Relative Importance of Sub-Components	Percentage of Cost of Sub-Components	Cost Index of Sub-Components
Staff	0.43	0.2800	1.53
Preparation	0.22	0.7000	0.31
Presentation	0.19	0.0180	10.50
Cooking	0.16	0.0011	145.40

In Table 19, the relative importance levels, cost percentages and target cost indices of the sub-components of the sample enterprise for food and beverage services are given. In line with the findings, the target cost index of all other sub-components of the food and beverage services

sub-component, except for the target cost index of the preparation sub-component, was above 1. This suggests that customers place a higher level of importance on relevant subcomponents than the costs incurred by delivering the sample to perform the service. Regarding the personnel sub-

component, which is one of the sub-components of food and beverage services, it may be necessary for the sample business to work with more qualified personnel. Customers' importance to the relevant subcomponent is higher than the cost percentage of the sample business. Customers attach more importance to the personnel in food and beverage services than other sub-components. In this case, it can be suggested that the sample enterprise ensures that its personnel working in the relevant service are trained in a more qualified way. A similar situation applies to the presentation sub-component. The service is

carried out at a lower cost than the importance given by the customers to the relevant sub-component. For this purpose, it can be recommended that the sample business diversify its presentation techniques. Here, the importance of the preparation sub-component is higher than the importance of the presentation sub-component. However, the opposite is the case with cost percentages. In this respect, the sample business may need to reduce costs for the preparation sub-component without reducing quality.

Table 20. Entertainment Services-Target Cost Indices of Components

Sub-Components	Relative Importance of Sub-Components	Percentage of Cost of Sub-Components	Cost Index of Sub-Components
Staff	0.59	0.95	0.62
Consumables	0.41	0.05	8.20

As can be seen in Table 20, since the majority of the cost in entertainment services belongs to the personnel sub-component, the target cost index of the sub-components remained below 1. This shows that the business spends more costs than the importance given by the customers to the relevant sub-component. The cost of the personnel sub-component of the sample enterprise for the relevant service is 95%. It can be

suggested that the sample business reduces personnel costs here. This situation should also be evaluated in terms of fixed costs. The target cost index for consumables was obtained above 1, indicating that the costs for the relevant sub-component are lower than the importance levels of the customers. For this purpose, the sample business can increase the variety of consumables used for the service.

Table 21. General Activities-Target Cost Indices of Components

Sub-Components	Relative Importance of Sub-Components	Percentage of Cost of Sub-Components	Cost Index of Sub-Components
Staff	0.32	0.8350	0.38
Cleaning Supplies	0.48	0.1320	3.60
Consumables	0.20	0.0325	6.15

Finally, target cost indices for general activities are created in Table 21. Among the importance levels of the components of general activities, the highest value belongs to cleaning materials. On the other hand, the highest value of the cost percentage belongs to the personnel sub-component. Therefore, the value of the personnel sub-component remained below 1 in the target cost indices. The target cost indices of the cleaning materials and consumables sub-components were found to be above 1. This shows that the sample business performs the service at a lower cost than

the importance given by the customers for the relevant sub-components. In this respect, the sample business may need to take actions to increase the functionality of the relevant sub-components.

After calculating the target cost indices of the sub-components of the services, the cost reduction targets should be calculated. For this, the target costs must be subtracted from the actual costs of the sample business. The equation for this is as follows.

$$\text{Target: Cost Reduction Per Room} = \text{Actual Cost Per Room} - \text{Target Cost Per Room}$$

Here, it is known that the actual cost per room for 2023 is 1,134.44 TL, and the target cost per room for 2024 is 1,500 TL. In ordinary cases, the target cost is expected to be lower than the actual cost. However, it is known that costs are increasing day by day in TL terms due to the inflationary environment that the Turkish economy has experienced recently. Accordingly, it is healthier in terms of method to calculate the cost reduction target based on the Dollar/TL exchange rate of the same day. As of 20.06.2023, the Dollar/TL exchange rate is 23.5770. As of 20.06.2024, it is 32.5711. Accordingly, the actual cost per room of the sample business is 48.12 dollars. The target cost per room of the sample business is 46.05 dollars. Therefore, the cost reduction target per room for the sample business is 2.07 in dollar terms.

3.4.3. Kaizen Costing Practice

Kaizen costing practice is carried out with some equations as a cost improvement method. The relevant equations are given below in order. While performing the Kaizen costing practice, the calculation was made by taking into account the Dollar/TL exchange rate in the cost calculations. Since the inflationary environment that the Turkish economy has experienced in recent times produces different results in cost calculations, the calculation was also made in the form of the Dollar/TL exchange rate.

1. *Final Actual Cost Per Room* = $\frac{\text{Total actual cost in the recent period}}{\text{Number of rooms sold recently}}$
2. *Current Period Total Estimated Cost* = *Final Actual Cost per Room* * *Current Period Estimated Room Sales*
3. *Current Period Total Kaizen Cost Target* = *Current period total estimated cost* – *Current period total target cost*
4. *Allocation Rate* = $\frac{\text{Costs directly controlled by a department}}{\text{Costs directly controlled by departments}}$

Total Kaizen Cost Target for a Department = *Current period total Kaizen cost target* * *Allocation rate*

Accordingly, the Kaizen costing practice of the study is as follows.

$$\text{Final Actual Cost Per Room} = \frac{139,760,171}{123,198}$$

Last Actual Cost Per Room = 1,134.44 TL

$$\text{Estimated Total Cost for the Current Period} = 1,134.44 * 150,000$$

Current Period Total Estimated Cost = TL 170,166,000

Since the actual cost per room of the sample business is 1,134.44 TL and the estimated room sales are 150,000, the total estimated cost of current importance is calculated as 170,166,000 TL. The total cost target for the current period is calculated with the help of the following formula.

$$\text{Current Period Total Cost Target} = 1,500 * 150,000$$

Current Period Total Cost Target = 225,000,000 TL

Since the target cost per room has been determined as 1,500 TL, the total cost target has been calculated as 225,000,000 TL.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Current Period Total Kaizen Cost Target} \\ = 170,166,000 - 225,000,000 \end{aligned}$$

Current Period Total Kaizen Cost Target = - 54,834,000 TL

The negative Kaizen cost target here is due to the extremely volatile nature of the Dollar/TL exchange rate in the 2023-2024 period. From June 20, 2023, to June 20, 2024, the Dollar/TL exchange rate increased by 38.15%. This has led to different results in cost calculations. If we perform the calculation based on the Dollar/TL exchange rate, it will be seen that the Kaizen cost target is also different. Accordingly, the calculations are given below.

While calculating the total estimated cost for the current period, the actual cost per room was calculated as 1,134.44 TL. The actual cost per room during this period was \$48.12 (1,134.44/23.5770). Therefore, the total estimated cost for the current period;

$$= 48.12 * 150,000$$

= \$7,217,430.

Likewise, in the calculation of the total cost target for the current period, the target cost per room has been determined as 1,500 TL. This value, together with the Dollar/TL exchange rate during the period, is the target cost per room of \$46.05 (1,500/32.5711). Accordingly, the total cost target for the current period;

= 46.05 * 150,000
= \$6,907,500.

Accordingly, the total Kaizen cost calculation for the current period;

= 7,217,430 – 6,907,500
= \$309,930.

The TL equivalent of this value is 10,094,761.02 TL. Looking at the allocation rates, since 5 different fields of activity were determined in the sample enterprise, the allocation rate was calculated separately for all of them.

$$\text{Front Office – Rooms Services Allocation Rate} = \frac{\text{Costs directly controlled by the front office/rooms department.}}{\text{Costs directly controlled by departments}}$$

$$\text{Front Office – Rooms Services Allocation Rate} = \frac{6,086,209.1}{58,812,632}$$

Front Office – Rooms Services Allocation Ratio = 0.10

$$\text{Housekeeping Allocation Rate} = \frac{\text{Costs directly controlled by the housekeeping department.}}{\text{Costs directly controlled by departments}}$$

$$\text{Housekeeping Allocation Rate} = \frac{15,698,611.9}{58,812,632}$$

Housekeeping Allocation Ratio = 0.27

$$\text{Food and Beverage Services Allocation Rate} = \frac{\text{Costs directly controlled by the food and beverage department.}}{\text{Costs directly controlled by departments}}$$

$$\text{Food and Beverage Services Allocation Rate} = \frac{28,194,141}{58,812,632}$$

Food and Beverage Services Allocation Ratio = 0.48

$$\text{Entertainment Services Allocation Rate} = \frac{\text{Costs directly controlled by the entertainment division.}}{\text{Costs directly controlled by departments}}$$

$$\text{Entertainment Services Allocation Rate} = \frac{1,241,963}{58,812,632}$$

Entertainment Services Allocation Ratio = 0.02

$$\text{General Activities Allocation Rate} = \frac{\text{Costs directly controlled by the general activities department.}}{\text{Costs directly controlled by departments}}$$

$$\text{General Activities Allocation Rate} = \frac{7,591,707}{58,812,632}$$

General Activities Allocation Ratio = 0.13

After determining the allocation rates of the service components/departments of the sample enterprise, the Kaizen cost target for each department was determined. While performing this process, the allocation rates of each

department are multiplied by the total Kaizen cost target. With this process, the cost targets that each component must reduce are achieved. Accordingly, the Kaizen cost target of the service components of the sample enterprise is as follows.

Front Office – Room Services Kaizen Cost Target

$$= \text{Front office – room services allocation rate} * \text{Total Kaizen cost target}$$

Front Office – Rooms Kaizen Cost Target = \$309,930*0.1
= \$30,993.

*Accommodation Services Kaizen Cost Target = Accommodation services allocation rate * Total Kaizen cost target*

Housekeeping Kaizen Cost Target = \$309,930*0.27
= \$83,681.1.

Food & Beverage Services Kaizen Cost Target

$$= \text{Food \& Beverage Services Allocation Rate} * \text{Total Kaizen Cost Target}$$

Food & Beverage Services Kaizen Cost Target = \$309,930*0.48

= \$148,766.4.

*Entertainment Services Kaizen Cost Target = Entertainment services allocation rate * Total Kaizen cost target*

Entertainment Services Kaizen Cost Target = \$309,930*0.02

= \$6,198.7.

*Kaizen Cost Target for General Activities = General activities allocation rate * Total Kaizen cost target*

General Activities Kaizen Cost Target = \$309,930*0.13

= \$40,290.9.

When all calculations are shown in a table, the following table emerges.

Table 22. Service Components-Kaizen Cost Target (\$)

Service Components	Kaizen Cost Target (\$)
Front Office – Rooms	30,993.00 \$
Housekeeping	83,681.00 \$
Food and Beverage Services	\$148,766.40
Entertainment Services	\$6,198.70
General Activities	40,290.90 \$
Total	309,930.00 \$

In Table 22, the Kaizen cost target hitting the service components is shown in dollars (\$). According to the findings, the highest value of Kaizen cost targets belongs to food and beverage services with \$148,766.4. The high target is due to the high allocation rate of the relevant service component.

3.4.4. Target Costing - Kaizen Convergence

The purpose of target costing is to determine the costs of the product or service before the production phase of the product or service is realized, in other words, while it is in the design phase, and to reduce the costs in order to reach the targeted value. After determining the target cost, the separation process is carried out for the product or service components and changes can be made in the application to achieve the target.

In this study, first of all, target costing practice was carried out for the sample business and it was determined to which service components and to what extent the target cost could be realized with the Kaizen costing method. In line with the 2023 annual report of the sample enterprise, the target costing was realized for 2024. The costs of which sub-components should be reduced in which section and which sub-components should be increased as a result of Kaizen costing are summarized in the following paragraphs.

In target costing, it is stated that the target cost indices of the service sub-components are 1. A

target cost index of 1 indicates that the cost incurred for the sub-components is equal to the importance level. If the index is above 1, it means that the relative importance of the component is higher than the component cost share. In other words, the business fulfills a service sub-component that customers attach more importance to at less cost. In this case, the business is expected to carry out development activities for the sub-component that is given more importance by the customers. If the index value is below 1, it means that the importance of the service sub-component determined by the customers is lower than the component cost share. In this case, the enterprise is required to carry out cost reduction activities for the relevant service sub-component.

The service cost index of the personnel sub-component, which is one of the sub-components of the sample enterprise for front office-rooms services, was calculated as 0.79. As a result, for the index below 1, it is seen that the component cost share is higher than the component importance. The target cost indices of the printed documents-stationery and consumables sub-components were calculated well above 1. The Kaizen cost target for front office-rooms services is set at \$30,993. Here, it is seen that the Kaizen cost target should be reduced over the personnel sub-component with a target cost index below 1. In other words, within the scope of the Kaizen cost target, the sample business needs to reduce costs in the personnel sub-component of the front office-rooms service. Other sub-components, such as printed documents, stationery and consumables, should increase functionality.

When the target cost indices of the sub-components of housekeeping services are examined, the target cost index in the personnel sub-component is calculated as 0.51, below 1, as in the front office-rooms services. Here, while the index for cleaning materials is 2.27, it is 6.84 for

amenities. The Kaizen cost target for housekeeping is calculated as \$83,681. Within the scope of the Kaizen costing target for housekeeping, the sample business should reduce costs in the personnel sub-component with a target cost index below 1. In other sub-components, the target cost index was above 1 because the importance levels of customers were higher than the service cost share. For this reason, it is necessary to increase the functionality of other components in accordance with the customer's importance.

The target cost indices for the sub-components of food and beverage services were calculated as 1.53 for the personnel component, 0.31 for the preparation component, 10.5 for the presentation component and 145.4 for the cooking component. Here, the enterprise's costs for the cooking component are low relative to customer-assigned importance. It is seen that customers attach importance to cooking and presentation services for food and beverage services, while the sample business has very low costs for these services. In this respect, the functionality of the relevant services should be increased. The Kaizen cost target for food and beverage service was calculated as \$148,766.4. This value is due to the high allocation rate of food and beverage services within the sample business. The allocation rate is obtained by dividing the costs directly controlled by the department (here, food and beverage service) by the costs directly controlled by the departments. The allocation rate for food and beverage services was calculated as 0.48. Therefore, 48% of the Kaizen costing target should be achieved in this service section. Since the target cost index of the preparation component is calculated as 0.31, the Kaizen cost target should be realized especially through this service sub-component. In other words, for the sample business Kaizen cost target, it is necessary to

reduce the costs in the preparation sub-component.

There are two sub-components in entertainment services, the target cost index of the personnel sub-component is calculated as 0.62 and the target cost of the consumables sub-component is calculated as 8.2. The Kaizen cost target for entertainment services is calculated as \$6,198.7. Here, reducing the costs of the personnel sub-component with an index value below 1 is important for the realization of the Kaizen cost target. In order to achieve the Kaizen cost target, the sample business must first reduce the costs of the personnel sub-component. For the consumables sub-component, it should carry out applications that increase functionality.

Finally, in general activities, the personnel sub-component has a target cost index below one. While the target cost index for cleaning materials is 3.6, the target cost index for consumables is 6.15. The Kaizen cost target for the department is calculated as \$40,290.9. In order to achieve the Kaizen cost target, the sample business should reduce the costs of the personnel sub-component within the department and implement practices that increase the functionality of other sub-components.

3.4.5. Kaizen Improvement Modeling within the Scope of Target Cost

In the calculations made so far, a modeling has been made in the form of distributing the expenses arising within the scope of the revenue-generating activities of the sample enterprise to the relevant departments with the Kaizen approach. Similar studies have been discussed with the same approach in the literature. However, looking at the 2023 data of the sample enterprise, as seen in Table 23, only 56% of the total expenses are expenses arising from income-generating activities.

Table 23. Share of Expenses in Total Expense (%)

	TL	USD	Ratio of Expenses to Total Expenses
Department Expenses			
Front Desk-Accommodation	23,213,848	984,597	17%
F&B	45,036,971	1,910,208	32%
Other	9,898,084	419,819	7%
Total Expenses	78,148,903	3,314,625	56%
Non-Revenue Departments (GGD)			

General Administrative Expenses	28,039,348	1,189,267	20%
GGD (Other) Expenses	33,571,920	1,423,927	24%
Business Wide			
Operating Total Expenses	139,760,171	5,927,818	100%

The share of General Administrative Expenses in total expenses is 20%, and the share of Non-Revenue Generating Departments such as financial affairs, technical, information systems, human resources, security is 24%. For this reason, when distributing the determined Kaizen cost target to service components, this distribution

should be distributed to 56% of the total expenses, and the remaining 44% should be distributed to General Administrative Expenses and Non-Revenue Generating Departments. With this approach, the share of service components from the total Kaizen cost target should be as follows.

Table 24. The Share Service Components Should Get from the Kaizen Cost Target

Service Components	Kaizen Cost Target (\$)	Distribution (%)	Constituents' Required Share (56%)
Front Office – Rooms	30,993.00	10	6%
Housekeeping	83,681.00	27	15%
Food and Beverage Services	148,766.40	48	27%
Entertainment Services	6,198.70	2	1%
General Activities	40,290.90	13	7%
Total	309,930.00	100	56%

Table 24 shows the shares that service components should receive from the Kaizen cost target according to the new situation described. In the first distribution, the share of the Front Office – Rooms department was 10%, while this share is 6% when General Administrative Expenses and Non-Revenue Generating Departments are taken into account. Likewise, the share of housekeeping services is 15% when it is 27%, food and beverage

services is 27% when it is 48%, entertainment services is 1% when it is 2%, and general activities is 7% when it is 13%. According to this calculation, the share of revenue departments in the Kaizen cost target is 56%, while the remaining 44% is allocated to general administrative expenses (20%) and non-revenue generating departments (24%). As such, the Kaizen cost target of \$309,930 is distributed to the components as follows.

Table 25. Kaizen Cost Target Distributed to All Expenses

Service Components	Distribution Rate	Kaizen Cost Target (\$)	Kaizen Cost Target (TL)
Front Office – Rooms	6%	17,356.00	565,306.62
Housekeeping	15%	46,861.00	1,526,326.04
Food and Beverage Services	27%	83,310.00	2,713,482.71
Entertainment Services	1%	3,471.00	113,050.38
General Activities	7%	22,563.00	734,900.43
Overhead	20%	61,986.00	2,018,952.20
Non-Revenue Departments	24%	74,383.00	2,422,742.65
Total	100	309,930.00	10,094,761.02

Table 25 shows the amounts of Kaizen cost targets distributed across all expenses in dollars and TL. The 2024 targets of the sample enterprise were taken and the improvements to be made in the relevant expense items in line with the calculated Kaizen cost target were reported to the business officials. Accordingly, it has been stated that a total of 10,094,761.02 TL can be reduced from the cost targets, including 565,306.62 TL from front office-rooms, 1,526,326.04 TL from housekeeping, 2,713,482.71 TL from food and beverage services, 113,050.38 TL from entertainment services, 734,900.43 TL from general activities,

2,018,952.20 TL from general administrative expenses and 2,422,742.65 TL from non-revenue departments.

It has been stated that improvements can be made in the personnel sub-component in rooms, housekeeping, entertainment and general activities, and in the preparation sub-component in food and beverage services. In addition, it was evaluated that the Kaizen cost reduction target could be achieved with improvements to be made in general administrative expenses and non-revenue departments.

Table 26. Financial Highlights - 2024

	Hedef	Realized	Deviation (+/-)
Department Revenues	TL	TL	
Front Desk-Accommodation	185,000,000	184,503,896	- 496,104
F&B	95,000,000	94,542,661	- 457,339
Other	20,000,000	21,968,206	1,968,206
Total Revenues	300,000,000	301,014,763	1,014,763
Department Expenses			-
Front Desk-Accommodation	38,000,000	36,102,078	1,897,922
F&B	80,000,000	76,472,821	3,527,179
Other	17,000,000	16,561,076	438,924
Total Expenses	135,000,000	129,135,974	5,864,026
Department Profitability			-
Front Desk-Accommodation	147,000,000	148,401,819	1,401,819
F&B	15,000,000	18,069,840	3,069,840
Other	3,000,000	5,407,130	2,407,130
Department Profit	165,000,000	171,878,789	6,878,789
Non-Revenue Departments (GGD)			-
General Management	55,000,000	52,479,711	2,520,289
GGD Total Expenses	45,000,000	42,387,729	2,612,271
Business Wide			-
Operating Total Expenses	235,000,000	224,003,414	10,996,586
Business Total Profit	65,000,000	77,011,349	12,011,349
Profitability (%)	22%	26%	

Efficiency was increased by switching to a flexible working model in rooms, housekeeping, entertainment and general activities and by planning training for the working personnel, and a total improvement of 2,336,846 TL was achieved by reducing the number of budgeted personnel, as seen in Table 26. In food and beverage services, product recipes were reviewed, and unnecessary details that did not affect service quality were removed and savings were achieved. In addition,

unit costs were reduced by making bulk purchases for products that can be stocked. Procurement activities were carried out with the online auction method and a competitive advantage was achieved. Thus, an improvement of 3,527,179 TL was achieved in the preparation sub-component. The number of vehicles used in general administrative expenses was reduced, and the vehicle and fuel tracking system was commissioned and 2,520,289 TL savings were

achieved. In non-revenue departments, personnel were reduced and energy costs, which constitute a large part of the expense, were saved by using timed and solar-powered illuminators. A total of TL 2,612,271 TL was saved in non-revenue departments. Thus, 10,996,586 TL savings were achieved in total expenses compared to the targeted amount.

4. CONCLUSION

With the increase in competition as a result of global developments, businesses have started to search for new ways to maintain or improve their position in the accommodation sector. Today, in competitive markets where prices are determined by the sector, businesses are faced with the fact that setting prices according to their costs may cause them to lose their competitive position. Due to their structure that can be easily copied and cannot be stocked, accommodation businesses cannot make a difference in the services they offer. For this reason, accommodation businesses can use profit margins as a tool or reduce their costs in order to make a difference against their competitors.

When the selling price of a product is determined by the market, that is, when the company cannot influence the price, it is natural for the manager to turn his eyes to costs. As an alternative to determining the selling price by adding a specific markup to the unit cost of the product, the firm can set a cost target to realize that markup. All processes implemented to achieve this cost target are called "target costing".

In general, it can be considered that when the cost is reduced, the quality may also decrease. However, of course, if the cost can be reduced without a reduction in quality acceptable to the customer, then a significant cost reduction can be mentioned. For this reason, this process, which is stated to coincide with product design, is a process that requires great attention. The issue becomes more complex, especially when it comes to multi-product businesses and there are concerns about what costs are associated with the products.

Target costing is an important cost management technique used in the development of new products and services and the improvement of existing services and product processes. For this reason, reducing costs by keeping the service quality constant or increasing it, especially in the accommodation sector, is one of the main goals of businesses. Here, the Kaizen costing technique,

which adopts the philosophy of continuous improvement, is also of great importance. Which components from which department will be improved and to what extent or their costs need to be reduced can be determined by the Kaizen costing technique. Therefore, it is desirable to reduce costs while making improvements in an integrated structure with target costing and Kaizen costing in the accommodation sector. Businesses that reduce their costs with the increase in competition can continue to increase their presence in the market.

In this study, which was carried out with the integrated use of target costing and Kaizen costing techniques, a sample business operating in the accommodation sector was examined. In the study carried out on the 2023 annual reports, target costing and Kaizen costing practices for 2024 were carried out.

In accordance with this purpose, first of all, the service sections of the sample enterprise were determined. For the target cost separation process, service sections are determined as front office-rooms, housekeeping, food and beverage services, entertainment services and general activities. Then, the sub-functions of each service section were determined. At this stage, the relative importance of the sub-functions was determined with a questionnaire directed to the customers. Each customer was asked to determine the importance levels of the sub-functions of the departments. With the data obtained, the relative importance of the sub-functions was determined. After determining the relative importance of the sub-functions, the cost of each sub-component was determined. Within the scope of the 2023 annual report, the costs of front office-rooms services, housekeeping, food and beverage services, entertainment services and sub-components of general activities were determined. In the next stage, the relative importance of the components that make up the service was determined. The calculation of the relative importance of the components that make up the service was carried out with the relative importance of the sub-functions of the services and the percentages of the service coverage of the sub-components of the services obtained from the enterprise. In the last stage for target costing, a target cost index of each service and its sub-components was created. It is desirable for the target cost index to be 1. According to the target cost index, the target cost indices of the personnel

sub-component of the front office-rooms, housekeeping, entertainment services and general activities services, and the preparation sub-component of the food and beverage services were calculated below 1. This shows that the business spends more costs than the importance given by the customers to the relevant sub-component. Especially in 4 service sections, the fact that the target cost index of the personnel sub-component is below 1 shows that the personnel expenses of the sample enterprise are high. For this, the cost reduction target of the sample business should start from the sub-components with a target cost index below 1.

Another application carried out is the Kaizen costing practice. Here, the last actual cost per room, the total estimated cost for the current period, the total cost target for the current period, the total Kaizen cost target for the current period, the allocation rate and the total Kaizen cost target of a section were determined. In the Kaizen costing practice, the analysis was based on the Dollar/TL exchange rate. This situation is related to the inflationary environment experienced in the relevant period. In the relevant period, the Dollar gained 38.15% against TL. Therefore, in the costing practice carried out in TL, the Kaizen costing target was calculated as negative. In order to correct this, an analysis was carried out on the Dollar/TL exchange rate and the total Kaizen cost target of the sample business was calculated as \$ 309,930.

The allocation rates of the service departments were calculated as 10% for front office-rooms services, 27% for housekeeping, 48% for food and beverage services, 2% for entertainment services and 13% for general activities. Allocation ratios are obtained by dividing the costs directly controlled by a department by the costs directly controlled by the departments. In this respect, the high allocation rate is due to the fact that the costs directly controlled by the department are relatively high compared to the costs directly controlled by the departments. Within the scope of the findings, the cost directly controlled by the department was realized in food and beverage services at the highest rate among the service departments. The lowest rate was realized in entertainment services. However, in the evaluation made on the 2023 data of the sample enterprise, it was determined that the share of the costs incurred by the revenue departments in total expenses was 56%, 20% of the expenses were due to general expenses and 24% were due to non-

revenue departments. Accordingly, the allocation rates have been revised again and calculated as 6% for front office-rooms services, 15% for housekeeping, 27% for food and beverage services, 1% for entertainment services, 7% for general activities, 20% for general administrative expenses and 24% for non-revenue departments.

Within the scope of the findings, the Kaizen cost targets of the service components were achieved by multiplying the total Kaizen cost target by the allocation rate determined for each department. Accordingly, the Kaizen cost target for front desk-rooms services is \$17,356, the Kaizen cost target for housekeeping is \$46,861, the Kaizen cost target for food and beverage services is \$83,310, the Kaizen cost target for entertainment services is \$3,471, the Kaizen cost target for general activities is \$22,563, the Kaizen cost target for general administrative expenses is \$61,986, and the Kaizen cost target for non-revenue departments is \$74,383.

As a result of the integrated use of target costing and Kaizen costing practices, the target cost index of the personnel sub-component of front office-rooms services, housekeeping, entertainment services and general activities was calculated as 0.79, 0.51, 0.62 and 0.38, respectively. In line with the Kaizen cost targets of the service departments, cost reduction practices should be carried out for the relevant sub-components. In particular, the fact that the target cost index of the personnel sub-component among the sub-components in almost all departments is below 1 shows that the personnel expenses of the sample enterprise are high. In this respect, in order to achieve Kaizen cost targets, it is necessary to reduce sample operating personnel costs. Personnel expenses of the sample enterprise include gross wages, bonuses and premiums, severance pay, notice pay, SSI employer's share and employee benefits. In this respect, a flexible working model has been adopted to reduce the personnel costs of the exemplary enterprise. In addition, along with training activities for existing employees, quality has been increased by enabling them to work in more qualified personnel positions. With the increase in quality, sales prices were also updated, and the share of personnel costs in total cost was indirectly reduced. In addition, in other businesses or other studies, increasing employee engagement, outsourcing, incorporating new technologies into business processes and reducing

personnel costs with hybrid working models can be achieved.

Among the sub-components of food and beverage services with a target cost index below 1, the preparation sub-component appears in the annual report as the cost of food and beverage sales. The Kaizen cost target of the relevant department constitutes 27% of the total Kaizen cost target. The Kaizen cost target for food and beverage services is \$83,310. In this respect, it is an important area within the total Kaizen cost target. Here, the fact that the target cost index of the preparation sub-component is below 1 indicates that the component cost share is higher than the component importance level. In other words, the cost share of the sub-component (preparation sub-component) is higher than the importance given by the customers. In this case, it is thought to achieve the cost reduction target for the sample operation preparation sub-component. However, this situation is directly related to the economy of the country. While the OECD average for food inflation for the period between June 2023 and 2024 was 4.7%, this rate was 68.5% for Türkiye. Therefore, food inflation has a great impact on the fact that the cost of the preparation sub-component, which consists of food and beverage sales costs of the food and beverage services department of the sample enterprise, is higher than the customer importance level. Here, the sample business has made a regulation regarding suppliers. Unit costs were tried to be reduced by making bulk purchases. In addition, competition conditions were created with the online tender procedure and more affordable materials were purchased. On the other hand, the product recipes were reviewed and unnecessary details that did not affect the quality were removed from the recipes.

In addition, improvements were made in general administrative expenses and non-revenue department expenses, which correspond to 44% of total expenses, and savings of 2,520,289 TL were achieved in general administrative expenses and 2,612,271 TL in non-revenue departments.

As a result, the goal of reducing costs by keeping the quality constant or increasing in the accommodation sector, where competition is quite high, can be achieved with modern costing methods. In this respect, target costing and Kaizen costing techniques were applied in this study. For subsequent studies, it may be recommended to carry out research with the integrated use of

different contemporary costing techniques. On the other hand, conducting a similar study in the same hotel and comparing the data for two years may be useful in order to observe the point of the study in the process. In addition, in order to reduce calculation errors to zero and to make healthier analyzes and comments, it can be recommended to benefit from artificial intelligence applications that have entered our lives with Industry 4.0 and are developing day by day. For businesses, it should be stated that success in cost targets will be achieved by using modern costing techniques. In addition, it should be recommended to employ qualified financial affairs personnel who will perceive and adopt this approach. Considering the contribution of the accommodation sector to the country's economy, the issue should also be on the agenda of the ministry and it is recommended to carry out the relevant studies.

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